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A COMPARISON OF PREDICTED AND MEASURED PROPERTIES OF
DOUBLY-ROTATED LITHIUM TETRABORATE RESONATORS

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Abstract

Recently, the authors have presented calculations of the properties expected for doubly-rotated lithium tetraborate resonators. The loci of cuts possessing both first and second order temperature compensation for the simple thickness modes of plate resonators driven by thickness-directed electric fields were identified. Lithium tetraborate plates cut to the nominal orientations of these loci have since been obtained and measurements have been undertaken to verify the predictions. The mode spectra, equivalent circuit parameters, and frequency-temperature behavior have been examined for the first, third, and fifth harmonics for all three simple thickness modes of the resonators. The observed values of frequency constants and piezocoupling are in good agreement with the predicted values. The measured temperature coefficients are less well in agreement with the predicted values.

Introduction

In a recent series of papers [1-5], the authors have presented calculations of the properties expected for doubly-rotated lithium tetraborate resonators. The calculations employed the one-dimensional approximation [6] and examined both thickness excitation (TE) and lateral excitation (LE) of thickness modes (TM) in plate resonators. Of primary interest were the wave velocities, piezocoupling, and temperature coefficients of frequency. The data of Shiosaki et al. [7] as listed in Table 1 were used in the calculations with one exception; the thermal expansion coefficients were used to calculate the temperature coefficients of density, rather than using the published values.

In carrying out the calculations over the entire primitive region of the material, the loci of cuts possessing both first and second order temperature compensation for TETM plate resonators were identified. One cut, employing the

extensional or 'a'-mode, with nominal angles of cut (YXwl)40°/33° has been given the designation of TA-cut. This cut is proposed for applications when frequency stability with temperature over an extended range is a requirement, jointly with moderate piezoelectric coupling. The other cut, employing the slow shear or 'c'-mode, with nominal angles of cut (YXwl)19°/56° has been designated as the TC-cut. This cut is proposed for applications demanding superior frequency stability with temperature, and piezocoupling values larger than available with quartz. In both cases, first- and second-order temperature compensation is predicted only for the fundamental harmonic when driven by thickness excitation.

Experimental Samples

In order to verify the predicted behaviors, a set of lithium tetraborate plates cut to the nominal orientations of the TA- and TC-cuts was obtained from a

TABLE 1. Li₂B₄O₇ MATERIAL CONSTANTS @ 25°C

Item	Value	T(1)	T(2)
		10 ⁻⁶ /K	10 ⁻⁹ /K ²
ε ^S ₁₁	78.8x10 ⁻¹² F/m	97.1	2800
ε ^S ₃₃	71.5x10 ⁻¹² F/m	545	2900
e ₁₅	0.472 C/m ²	-1050	-900
e ₃₁	0.290 C/m ²	-573	-6910
e ₃₃	0.928 C/m ²	-600	-6500
c ^E ₁₁	135. x10 ⁹ N/m ²	-81	-440
c ^E ₁₂	3.57x10 ⁹ N/m ²	3370	-17400
c ^E ₁₃	33.5 x10 ⁹ N/m ²	465	-2300
c ^E ₃₃	56.8 x10 ⁹ N/m ²	364	-1800
c ^E ₄₄	58.5 x10 ⁹ N/m ²	-18.1	500
c ^E ₆₆	46.7 x10 ⁹ N/m ²	-272	-450
α ₁₁	-----	11.1	5.6
α ₃₃	-----	-3.74	21
ρ	2439 kg/m ³	-2.01	-31.8

material grower [8]. The plates are of plano-plano geometry, 14mm diameter, 168.4 μm thick, with both sides optically polished. The plates were cleaned using organic solvents and a UV/ozone cleaner, then electroded, mounted, and sealed in two-point mount HC-6 type cold-weld enclosures. A nominal mass loading of 0.48% was obtained with 300Å Cr/1200Å Au electrodes of 5.34 mm diameter.

Mode Spectra

The mode spectra of the resonators were examined using an HP8753B Network Analyzer/HP85046A S-Parameter Test Set in conjunction with HP85160A Measurement Automation Software [9]. Figure 1 shows the observed mode spectrum of the TA-cut and Figure 2 shows the mode spectrum of the TC-cut. The observed frequencies of the various modes and their harmonics are listed in Tables 2 and 3 for the TA- and TC-cut respectively, along with certain other quantities of interest. The observed frequencies are in good agreement with the predictions, as are the observed values of piezocoupling. Note that for the TA-cut b-mode, a $Q \cdot f$ product of $2 \cdot 3 \times 10^{13}$ is observed. This high value is consistent with other lithium-based

TABLE 2. TA-CUT OBSERVED FREQUENCIES

Mode	M	f_R [MHz]	Q [10^3]	τ_1 [fs]	k [%]	b
a	1	21.041	1	6912	13	0.42
a	3	63.860	21	118	10	0.24
a	5	106.490	32	47	9.5	0.22
b	1	15.154	350	30	1.4	0.88
b	3	45.419	450	8	1.2	0.68
b	5	76.017	147	14	1.7	--
c	1	10.718	5	2884	17	0.69
c	3	32.537	21	234	15	0.47
c	5	54.284	37	82	13	0.41

TABLE 3. TC-CUT OBSERVED FREQUENCIES

Mode	M	f_R [MHz]	Q [10^3]	τ_1 [fs]	k [%]	b
a	1	20.095	2	4449	19	0.49
a	3	61.346	11	246	15	0.33
a	5	102.365	23	68	12	0.22
b	1	14.275	180	62	2.3	0.86
b	3	42.805	163	23	1.9	0.58
b	5	71.298	140	19	0.5	0.11
c	1	9.408	3	5524	25.5	0.89
c	3	29.017	12	456	20.3	0.50
c	5	48.400	50	64	8.4	0.09

Figure 1. Mode spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ TA-cut resonator driven by thickness excitation.

Figure 2. Mode spectrum of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ TC-cut resonator driven by thickness excitation.

Figure 3. Measured response of the fundamental harmonic of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ TA-cut 'a'-mode.

Figure 4. Measured response of the fundamental harmonic of the $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ TC-cut 'c'-mode.

piezoelectrics such as LiNbO_3 and LiTaO_3 . The motional time constant τ_1 is equal to $1/(2\pi f_R Q)$.

Figures 3 and 4 show respective views of the TA-cut fundamental 'a'-mode and TC-cut fundamental 'c'-mode in the vicinity of resonance. The presence of unwanted modes is noted in both cases. For the units tested here, the fundamental harmonic of any thickness mode was least afflicted by unwanted modes, while the harmonics suffered progressively increasing interference from unwanted modes. The implied loss of energy trapping with increasing harmonic is reflected in the one-dimensional electroded fraction of the active area denoted as b in Tables 2 and 3 [10-12].

Equivalent Circuit Parameters

The equivalent electrical circuit parameters of the resonators have been examined for the fundamental, third, and fifth harmonics for all three TE modes of the resonators. The measurements were made using two techniques:

1) HP4191A RF Impedance Analyzer/FLUKE 6060A Synthesizer with PTI developed software [13],

2) HP8753B Network Analyzer/HP85046A S-Parameter Test Set with HP85165A Resonator Measurement Software (implements EIA-512) [14].

Some difficulty was experienced in the measurement process due to the previously noted interference from unwanted modes.

The results of the equivalent circuit parameter measurements are summarized in Tables 4 and 5 for the TA- and TC-cuts, respectively.

TABLE 4. TA-CUT EQUIVALENT ELECTRICAL CIRCUIT PARAMETERS

Mode	M	$R_1[\Omega]$	$L_1[\text{mH}]$	$C_1[\text{fF}]$	$Co[\text{pF}]$
a	1	39.5	0.325	175	12.07
a	3	10.7	0.565	11.0	11.87
a	5	13.0	0.625	3.6	12.27
b	1	16	60	1.85	12.41
b	3	50	78	0.16	11.80
b	5	124	38	0.11	11.62
c	1	10.3	0.80	280	11.76
c	3	10.9	1.1	21.5	11.21
c	5	12	1.27	6.8	11.93

TABLE 5. TC-CUT EQUIVALENT ELECTRICAL CIRCUIT PARAMETERS

Mode	M	$R_1[\Omega]$	$L_1[\text{mH}]$	$C_1[\text{fF}]$	$Co[\text{pF}]$
a	1	13.4	0.19	332	11.30
a	3	9.9	0.27	24.8	12.08
a	5	11.3	0.40	6.05	12.08
b	1	12.0	24	5.2	11.73
b	3	58.6	35.4	0.39	11.61
b	5	615	190	0.03	11.29
c	1	8.7	0.46	635	12.07
c	3	11.4	0.74	40	10.93
c	5	24	4.0	2.65	11.49

Temperature Behavior

The frequency-temperature behavior of the zero-temperature coefficient cuts was measured using an IEC-444 pi-network transmission measurement system which has been described previously [15], and is currently being upgraded. The upgrade includes the incorporation of an HP8508A Vector Voltmeter which was used in conjunction with a modified version of the Stimulus-Response Software listed in HP Product Note 8508-2 [16]. Due to the presence of the unwanted modes, it was necessary to measure the frequency spectrum as a function of temperature and extract the data for each particular mode from the measured spectra.

Figures 5 and 6 show respectively the frequency-temperature behavior of the predicted zero-temperature coefficient modes of the TA- and TC-cuts. Although the measured first-order temperature coefficients show reasonable agreement with the predicted values, the second-order temperature coefficients are less well in agreement with the predicted values. The predicted and measured temperature coefficients of frequency of all the modes and harmonics examined here are summarized in Tables 6 and 7 for the TA- and TC-cuts respectively.

Figure 5. TA-cut 'a'-mode fundamental harmonic frequency-temperature behavior.

Figure 6. TC-cut 'c'-mode fundamental harmonic frequency-temperature behavior.

Conclusions

The predicted values of the first-order temperature coefficients of frequency $T_f^{(1)}$ show reasonable agreement with the measured values, but the predicted values of the second-order temperature coefficients of frequency $T_f^{(2)}$ do not agree well with the measured values. Although $\text{Li}_2\text{B}_4\text{O}_7$ shows promise as a piezoelectric material exhibiting the desirable properties of high Q, high coupling, and zero-temperature behavior, the design of resonant devices will require a substantially improved knowledge of the basic material constants.

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TABLE 6. TA-CUT PREDICTED AND MEASURED FREQUENCY-TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR

Mode	M	Predicted		Measured			
		$T_f^{(1)}$	$T_f^{(2)}$	$T_f^{(1)}$	$T_f^{(2)}$	$T_f^{(3)}$	T_i
a	1	+1	-26	-21	-202	+186	+387
a	3	-26	-151	-28	-67	+48	+501
a	5	-30	-166	-29	-66	+45	+511
b	1	-64	+472	-76	-49	--	---
b	3	-64	+475	-8	-5	--	---
b	5	-64	+476	-14	+5	--	---
c	1	-80	+219	-11	-4	--	---
c	3	-107	+113	-14	+4	-26	+83
c	5	-111	+100	-14	+5	-10	+199

Units: $T_f^{(1)}$ [$\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$], $T_f^{(2)}$ [$\times 10^{-9}/\text{K}^2$],
 $T_f^{(3)}$ [$\times 10^{-12}/\text{K}^3$], T_i [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

TABLE 7. TC-CUT PREDICTED AND MEASURED FREQUENCY-TEMPERATURE BEHAVIOR

Mode	M	Predicted		Measured			
		$T_f^{(1)}$	$T_f^{(2)}$	$T_f^{(1)}$	$T_f^{(2)}$	$T_f^{(3)}$	T_i
a	1	+39	-35	+46	-234	+461	+195
a	3	-10	-337	-2	-140	+221	+236
a	5	-15	-372	-5	-129	+175	+270
b	1	-31	+217	-47	-86	+216	+157
b	3	-31	+219	-47	-83	+109	+277
b	5	-31	+219	-47	-85	+100	+307
c	1	-3	+25	+2	-277	+324	+309
c	3	-47	-242	-58	-167	+235	+262
c	5	-52	-272	-63	-172	+256	+249

Units: $T_f^{(1)}$ [$\times 10^{-6}/\text{K}$], $T_f^{(2)}$ [$\times 10^{-9}/\text{K}^2$],
 $T_f^{(3)}$ [$\times 10^{-12}/\text{K}^3$], T_i [$^{\circ}\text{C}$]

samples, and the Frequency Control and Timing Branch of ETDL for processing the plates into resonators.

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